

THE EFFECT OF VARIOUS MEYERS AND COMBINATIONS OF ORGANIC RESIDUES PLACED UNDER ALFALFA ON THE BIOLOGICAL ACTIVITY OF THE SOIL

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Annotation.

This article gives the results of the study of various combinations of Meyers of guzapoya and anti-wilt preparations under Bede in reducing wilt infection and increasing resistance to bedani wilt infection and biological activity of the soil.

Keywords.

soil ,organic and mineral ugits, cassava ,wilt, fungi, propagule, urea, guzapoya, pathogenic, olgin, ammonia water.

Introduction

One of the main factors in increasing the yield of agricultural crops is the maintenance of soil with organic matter.

This not only increases soil fertility and crop yields, but also increases the biological activity of the soil, as a result of which the incidence of usimans with various diseases is reduced.

Organic matter is considered the main source of energy for the development of soil organisms, and its decomposition leads substances to a biological circulatory action.

Mineral deposits and the presence of organic residues create various conditions for the development of microflora in the soil yaratadi.Ug ' with the introduction of dogs, the microflora of the soil changes after various domesticated crops, without binding to the amount and composition of organic matter.

The increase in the yield of geese with the introduction of organic and mineral ugits is not only due to the fact that it is able to absorb nutrients, but also due to an artificial increase in the activity of the root system.

The positive effect of organic and mineral ugits is that humic acids in organic substances, physiologically active substances of the auxin type affect the exchange

of common substances in the plant organism, providing an opportunity to use mineral food Mulberry. Vitamins and other substances in the composition of local ugit have a positive effect on plant [1-5].

The biological environment of the soil actively influences the nutrition of plants through the root. Therefore, the enslavement of organic and mineral ugit is an important factor in increasing the yield of geese and other rural hujalik crops in the active use of nutrients. The effect on the development of mold, overwintering organic matter and acid residues begins only when they come to the state of mass of humus, which is processed in the microbial soil.

Thus, the effect of humus is determined not only by its nutritional properties, but also by the presence of an excess of biotic substances in its composition - vitamins, auxins, antibiotics. For example, a well-rotted local ugit contains thiamine and biotin, while Campot and Spike straw contain substances of the type vitamin V, riboflavin, heteroauxin aniqangan. Ug with the introduction of dogs and organic residues, the content of carbon two oxides in the soil air increases. Dividing Root and angiz residues in the soil accelerates the process of mineralization. The composition and amount of organic residues in the soil affect the microbiological processes that go in it kursatadi. Ug with the introduction of dogs, they become influential factors that change the biological properties of the soil. The amount of nitrogen provides a positive effect on the process of accumulation in the soil of micro-organisms, which cut off organic residues [6-10].

For these purposes, the main emphasis in cotton growing was on alfalfa in crop rotation. Beda, beda is the main crop in the exchange of geese, it satisfies the requirements of raising soil fertility and livestock.

It is considered the best domesticated crop of the goose, which improves the structure of the soil and enriches it with nitrogen under irrigated conditions.

Protection against diseases and pests is of great importance in increasing the yield of rural hujalik crops. Because they reduce the yield of crops and its quality, cause great harm, and ultimately negatively affect the fertility of the soil.

Literature analysis shows that beda is infected with wilt in very populous states. Damage from productivity is millions of dollars. For example, in Canada, transmission from Wilt is estimated to be around 250 million dollars. (Guseva I dr. 1986) to Bede vertisillez wilt disease in contrast to data from various state researchers V. alboatrum and V. dahlia causes.

In England, Isaac (1977), L. Isaac, A.T. In liioi (1978) 7 scientists reported that bedani vertisillez sulish disease is rapidly spreading and causing great harm to productivity.

The decrease in yield occurs with the flaking of the plant leaves and the destruction of the entire plant [11-15].

Bedani wilt has been diagnosed with ham in the islands of Hokkaidō, Japan. In the irrigated lands of Southern California, bedani was diagnosed with Wilt. A that alboatrum is the causative agent. B. Howell & H.S. The Ervins identified (1990)

Varieties of alfalfa planted in the Republic of Uzbekistan are not infected with wilt, but in one rotation of crop rotation for a very high density of Wilt infection in the soil - there are not enough so-called raw materials to reduce activity in crop rotation of the Bede and damage to the geese with this disease. Long years of monoculture gout planting have caused wilt's disease to spread to the Dome, now bedani needs a few rotations to reduce its damage.

M.A. Karimov (1971) 2's annual scientific work of kup in Urta Asie found fungal parasites, bacterial and viral diseases in the kup son, which damage the Bede in various developmental phases. However, the author did not take into account the disease of the bedani vertisillium sulish, caused by the vertisillium fungus.

N. S. Data from Mirpulatova (1978) 3, R. Sh. Tellyayev (1988) 4 and others indicate that Kura Verticillium dahlia is infected with Kleb's fungus, even three years of overstressing the bed cannot touch the intensity of the disease. In connection with this, it is necessary to develop special complex agrotadbirs along with preventive measures to increase soil fertility and soil biological activity at the same time as waiting for strong damaged soils with Wilt resistance and resistance of Bede to wilt infection. It is known that the rational use of mineral and organic uigits in increasing the yield of alfalfa has a great acumen. However, in the context of typical glacial soils, no studies have been carried out at the same time to enslave organic matter and anti-wilt preparations. At the same time, on soils with a natural strong infection with Wilt, various organic chemevium substances placed under the Alfalfa were not hit by the effect on the yield of alfalfa and geese [16-21].

Research object and methodology

Related to Holda the main task of the study is to determine the effect of various organic chemevium substances placed in the soil on the density of the verticillium dahlia Kleb fungus ni. The main component of the study is bulib, field experiment injection and the implementation of the necessary complex

agrotechnical measures field infection of the Tashkent-1 variety with the previous wilt fungus 80%, and the infection density of 60% in the case of the 108-f variety 666.6 propagule 1g in dry soil that is, the field is of a. Experiments were carried out on the central experimental base of Uppiti. Guzapaya is crushed with an aggregate of KIR-1,5, local ugit is half rotten.

The experimental scheme is as follows:

Option 1-control (every year the gooseberry is taken) :option 2-14t/ha gooseberry:option 3-14 t/ha gooseberry is processed into a kayta with a 20% urea solution:option 4-local fertilizer to 30 t/ha:option 5-local lead to 30 t/ha, take 100 kg/ha and ammonia water to 1500kg/ha.

The experimental variants were driven to a depth of 40 cm, making them of good quality with a PPN-40 brand plug after burning. In early spring, for optimal periods, bedani was replanted with the Tashkent-1 variety rizatorfin (200g rizatorfin 20 kg/ha alfalfa seed). The covering crop is the pomegranate variety of rye.

Verticillium dahlia Kleb fungus wilt fungus infection density decreased to 550 propagules.

On such soils, the result of anti-wilt measures is very low. Giving him a yerdam needs other methods of struggle that increase his activity against Wilt while improving bedani's usishi.

Research results and their discussion

That said, when 14 t/ha guzapoya is processed with 20% urea, its activity against Wilt increases. Local ug injection of 30t/ga increases the density of Wilt infection. According to the quantitative calculation of Verticillium dahlia Kleb fungi in the soil, in the control option (a gooseberry is taken every year), the first year is 600, the second year is 600, the third year is 550 propagules, 14t/ha gooseberries and 14t/ha gooseberries in the appropriate case in variants processed with a 20% urea solution--600,650,450,350,350,300.

Verticillium dahlia Kleb fungal quantitative calculation of most Cup fungi quantitative calculation of the most Cup pathogen reduction of density was observed in the third option. 550,350,350,300 per Control. The kimevi method gives a high result, however, it should be noted that khattaki did not manage to clean the soil from Wilt fungi by taking complex measures of struggle. From the data of the study, we found that in such soils, 14t/ha of guzapoyani is processed with a 20% urea solution, complex measures of struggle as a mandatory measure in strong areas of the disease, namely, local ugit per 30 t/ha, fungicide per 100 kg/ha, and

enslaving water with ammonia per 1500 kg/ha is an environmentally and economically acceptable method. By driving the guzapoya under the Alfalfa, the activity of nitrogen-fixing bacteria increases and the nitrogen in the atmosphere is disconnected in the presence of a carbohydrate that results from the decomposition of the guzapoya [1-5].

The elongated nitrogen element is then converted into protein compounds. This is a major source of increased soil fertility and enhanced soil biological activity.

Conclusion

Based on data from scientific research work, we came to the following conclusion:

Bedani's activity against Wilt increased when-14t / ga guzapoya was processed with 20% urea.

- Verticillium dahlia Kleb suggests quantitative calculation of the fungus that the decrease in the density of the most cop pathogen is also observed in the variant processed with a urea solution of 20% to 14 t/ha usha.

- As a mandatory event in areas where Vilt infection is strongly prevalent, a complex struggle measure can be called local ughit at 30 t/ha, olgin fungicide at 100 kg /ha and ammonia water at 1500 kg/ha .

Under the Alfalfa, various types of meyerda guzapoya and its combinations, chemevi substances are the main source in increasing soil fertility and enhancing its biological activity .

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